

GLOBALIZATION AND TEACHER EDUCATION

Dr.Vilas Ransure

Asso.Prof.Adhyapak Mahavidyala, Araneshwar, Pune

Rashmi Joshi

Asst.Prof. S.N.D.College of Education, Bhabhulgaon, Yeola (Nashik)

ABSTRACT:-

India has the second largest system of schooling in the world. About five million school teachers are working in the country at different levels of schooling. In India, not only in the school system but also in the social system as a Catalyst of change and development throughout the present system of teacher education in our country, one can say without any fear of contradiction that it is in deep crisis. It is sad that in spite of appointing several commissions and committees by the government we have failed to create teacher education programmes tailor made to meet the needs of the present day society in India. At present we are confronted with challenges of knowledge explosion, revolutionary, changes in information and communication technology, value crisis, social religious conflicts and tension etc. unless the future teachers are made sensitive to all these challenges. It is difficult for anyone to survive as a teacher and play the role expected of him. The phenomenon of globalization is considered as the most wide spread trend our century has ever witnessed. So in this century teacher education faced it of challenger in the content of Globalization.

INTRODUCTION:-

Globalization is a term used to describe the changes in societies and world economy that are result of dramatically increased trade and cultural exchange. In economic context it refers almost exclusively to the effects of trade, trade liberalization. In general sense “Globalization” means closer contract between different parts of the world, with increasing possibilities of personal exchange, mutual understanding and friendship between “World Citizens” and creation of a

global civilization. It increases relations among members of an institution in different parts of the world it also shares a number of characteristics with internationalization and is used interchangeably, although some prefer to use globalization to emphasize the erosion of the nation, state or national boundaries.

Globalization is today a trend, not just in economics, commercial and technological fields, but also in education. Globalization indicates “Inter connectivity of Technologies”. These technologies have rapidly made the world a “Global Village”. They have shrunk geographical frontiers, National organizations, individuals, business and commercial corporations are integrated by globalization. Even the scientific community is becoming a world community. The scientific community shares concept, exchanges Ideas, collaborates on projects and uses international standards and benchmarks.

To produce human resources with high quality, we need education with a high quality. In fact, according to the demand of the global challenges, we need to improve the quality of education and develop educational standards that contain global and international issues.

GLOBALIZATION AND EDUCATION

Globalization is the major aspect of the changed world environment. It challenges our established view on “Knowledge Production”. And removes learning from a traditionally stable position to a far some flexible idea of the “accumulation of new knowledge”. Both globalization and the flexible accumulation of knowledge have been made possible through two main inter-related historical occurrences.

Time and space have got compressed as a result of rapid development in communication and information technology.

There has been an over lapping of economic political and social cultural and cross currents since the collapse of the communist bloc and socialist market economics.

The social, cultural and political changes that have occurred in the recent past have Taken the concept of education and training well beyond the rational parameters of

university and college teaching and learning, into the broader economic and political sphere.

The privileged position held by institutions as places of learning has come under scrutiny, as also the whole culture of education and training in particular – how, where and for what purposes learning can and should take place. New concepts such as flexible learning has come under scrutiny, as also the whole culture of education and training in particular – how, where and for what purposes learning can and should take place. New concepts such as flexible learning work, place learning and distributed learning work, place learning and distributed learning have emerged, either in competition or in parallel with established concepts of education and training, thereby broadening the existing educational provisions and types of providers.

GLOBALIZATION AND OBJECTIVES OF EDUCATION

Globalization has brought in dogmatic changes in the field of education traditionally, objective of education were-

- 1) Physical and intellectual development of child.
- 2) Inclusion of Values.
- 3) Self and social knowledge and
- 4) Vocational training.

education is power

CHALLENGES AHEAD OF A TEACHER EDUCATION IN GLOBALIZATION.

1) Research in Teacher Education:-

Enhanced scope of Teacher education requires researches and studies to visualize scope of teacher education in the context of globalization. Research must respond to the area of policy issues, curriculum issues, evaluation systems, classroom practices, training strategies, value inculcation, school community relationship, technology mediated education, quality in education, interactive education, Inclusive education, practice teaching school etc.

2) Technology and Competency based Curriculum:-

The competency based curriculum represents an approach to instructions, which emphasize the application of the knowledge in a manner, which may be

observe or measured. Competency based curriculum guides focus on a comprehensive view of each course of study, which is delineated into its essential

components listing of most important objectives to be mastered and competencies which every student should be able to demonstrate often instruction is completed. Competency based lesson, which change the students in activities designed to apply learning with an increased emphasis on higher order thinking skills. Students are evaluated not only on knowledge, but also primarily on their ability to perform tasks associated with knowledge acquired.

NCTE in the general body meeting held on 17th August 2000 decided that “Information and Communication Technology literacy” should be made a compulsory part of B.Ed course. The word has entered in the information age by information explosion. The human brain has the privileged faculties of thinking, imagination and creativity. Any system of education, need to visualize the role of the future teacher. The teacher is not an instructor or task master; he is a helper and guide. The tree principle of trenching is that nothing can be taught. His business to suggest and not to impose. He does not actually train the pupil’s mind he only shows him how to perfect his instruments of knowledge so in the context of globalization curriculum should be needed Technology based.

3) Professionalism:-

The education standard will improve if all the teachers have global perspective, well prepared and provided with on going professional development and appropriate support.

4) Use of Integrated Technology:-

A growing challenge in education is, establishing and implementing strategies to develop the skills and knowledge necessary for the teacher to essentially use technology as instruction tool. The extent to which teacher is prepared to infuse technology into curriculum and instruction is major contextual factor.

5) Mobility of the Teachers across the globe:-

There is an increase in demand for Indian teachers in a many countries. The teachers need to be trained to be competent in the global market.

6) Adaptability:-

Teachers need to be adapted to the socio-economic and cultural diversities of the students in order to complete in the international sphere.

7) Quality Education:-

The words use to describe quality are in terms of expense, goodness, beauty, truth, idealness, rarely as per status and positional advantage. Quality is term used to describe the higher living organism, human being to the non-living things. That is A to Z on earth described in terms of quality.

We are now more interested in the quality in teacher education. High quality teacher education is one more challenge which is successes caters to the following conditions without any bias.

- Staff pattern as prescribed by NCTE.
- Infrastructure catering to the needs of teaching learning situations.
- Effective technique assessment.
- Effective learning outcome assessment.

8) The need to favor the development of skills long side knowledge:-

The phenomenon of globalization as helped to widen the gap between those who globalized and those who are globalized of the process at the local, National, Regional and International levels. Teaching to live together is synonymous with developing an understanding and appreciation of interdependence in spirit of respect for the value of pluralism, mutual understanding and peace.

CONCLUSION :-

Education plays a vital role to overcome many challenges and to maintain peace in the globe. Global challenges that influence all areas of human life in the world are conditions that are naturally going on as the consequence of the rapid development of science and technology. It is impossible to avoid but have to be faced by using resources with high quality especially human resources. Teacher's quality is the keyword for insuring the quality of education. Qualified competent teachers will not be able to carry out their task professionally without the conditions that support their tasks.

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